

Hardware Laboratories for Power Electronics and Motor Drives Distance Learning Courses

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Abstract -- This paper describes the new Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based power electronics and drives laboratories used for graduate teaching and research at the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS). Since the hardware is controllable through an FPGA based controller via a personal computer (PC), the laboratory experimental set up can be accessed by students located outside NPS through the internet. These new remotely controlled, real time, power laboratories are among the first experiments of this kind in the United States and they have been greeted by the power-track students with enthusiasm.

Index Terms-- Field programmable gate arrays, distance learning education, remotely controlled laboratories, DC motor drives, power electronics.

I. INTRODUCTION

An important part of engineering education is the laboratory experience. In particular most of the courses in Electrical Engineering have laboratory hours involving experiments which can be either computer projects (data analysis, simulations) or implementations on actual hardware. With the proliferation of distance learning (DL) and continuing education courses, the need for extending the laboratory experience to remotely located students has increased. Software laboratories, based on computer simulations, are effective in reinforcing the basic concepts learned in class. However hardware based laboratories offer a more complete experience including instrumentation operation, visual feedback and experimental measurements.

Remote controlled laboratories have been recently developed as a means to provide distance learning students with the same laboratory experience that resident students enjoy. References [1] through [10] present several examples of power electronics and drives laboratories which can be accessed remotely, most of them implemented in Europe and Asia. Very little work has been found to date in the USA [5] as shown in the survey presented in [6].

A state of the art FPGA based "student design center" (SDC) has been applied to research and curriculum at the

Naval Postgraduate School (NPS) [11] for the last four years. Several SDCs have been in use to implement user-friendly power electronics and electric drives laboratories, as well as multiple Master of Science theses and research projects [12], [13]. Each SDC includes an FPGA development board and two custom printed circuit boards (PCBs) with A/D converters, voltage and current sensors and an encoder interface. The SDC allows the user to control hardware and acquire waveforms in the laboratory via a PC interface. This paper presents the SDC in detail and also the web-interface recently created in order to make the SDC available to remotely located students taking DL courses. An example of a simple web controlled motor drive laboratory is presented together with the simulations used in the classroom to teach the theory behind the hardware demonstration. The impact of the new laboratories on the students' educational experience is also reported to complete the paper.

II. FPGA BASED HARDWARE LABORATORIES SET UP

Fig. 1 shows a block diagram of a power laboratory workstation including the SDC hardware and computer aided design (CAD) tools, a Semikron power module [17], passive components, electric machines and measuring instruments. Fig. 2 shows a photograph of the laboratory workbench with all the components labeled.

A. The Student Design Center (SDC)

The SDC is the enabling technology for the innovative power electronics and drives hardware experiments which have been in use at NPS for the past four years. Several workstations such as the one shown in Fig. 2 are used with hardware experiments including laboratories for the power electronics and machine classes, student theses' hardware validation and research projects. The SDC includes hardware and CAD tools. The SDC hardware is shown in Fig. 3 and includes the following electronic components:

- a Xilinx Virtex IV development board [14],
- a power supply to provide logic DC voltages from the

AC input,

- a custom PCB with 4 LEM current sensors and 4 voltage sensors,
- a custom PCB with A/D converters and gate driver outputs which interfaces to the FPGA development board and the power converter.

Communication between the PC and the FPGA occurs via a JTAG (Joint Test Action Group or IEEE Standard 1149.1) programming cable.

Fig. 1: SDC based power laboratory workstation block diagram

The SDC CAD tools include a computer with the software packages Simulink/Matlab with Xilinx’s “System Generator” [15], “ISE Foundation” and “Chipscope Pro Analyzer” [16].

Fig. 4 shows how each software package is used in the SDC software design process. Such process minimizes the simulation to hardware translation time because the user does not need to have any knowledge of VHDL, the hardware description language for VHSICs (Very High Speed Integrated Circuits). The power converter is simulated using the widely available Simulink/Matlab software with the addition of the System Generator’s blockset. The System Generator blocks must be used to design the power converter control system so that the Simulink model can be converted into VHDL code to program the FPGA chip. The Xilinx software ISE Foundation generates the final FPGA programming file and programs the FPGA through the JTAG cable.

The SDC allows several power converter topologies to be studied experimentally with any combination of control or modulation strategy. When the SDC is used to perform laboratory experiments the students use a PC to interact with the hardware (turn on/off, change loads, etc...). This is true for resident and remote students. The measurements required to complete the laboratory report are made using an oscilloscope. While the resident students interact with the oscilloscope using the knobs and buttons on the instrument’s front panel, the remote students control the oscilloscope using their web browser. Both groups of students acquire the oscilloscope plots and data via the instrument’s web page shown in Fig. 12. Details about the laboratory user interface are presented in section IV.

Fig. 2: SDC based workstation as implemented in the NPS Power Laboratory

A. B. Safety and Remote Operation

The power electronics and electric drives laboratories are

designed with the student’s safety in mind. The control panel available to the student does not allow the student to over-

stress the hardware so the student cannot accidentally cause damage to the equipment. A laboratory experiment can be performed only when a laboratory technician is present. This applies to resident as well as remote students. While the resident students can turn on the main power supply for the experiment and select the input voltage using a variac, the remote students rely on the laboratory technician to turn on the power. Then, they have full control of the experiment from a web browser and can perform on the internet all required measurements as described in section IV.

Fig. 3: SDC Control Electronics

Fig. 4: Computer aided design architecture

III. THE WEB INTERFACE FOR REMOTE CONTROL OF THE SDC

The remote students interact with the laboratory experiment through a main Web Server, as shown in the block diagram of Fig. 5. The server pages can display various instrument data, instructions and live video/audio on the same page. For a remote laboratory website, several interconnected web pages are created using HTML tabs. Fig.

6 shows, as an example, how the website looks like for the simple DC motor drive laboratory presented in section IV. The web server interprets the student input, such as on/off buttons and passes that information to the Xilinx Chipscope [16] Server. All data returned from the experiment equipment is made available to the student through the server. The Chipscope server receives commands from the web server to run the experiment. The Chipscope debugger creates an interface between the computer and the FPGA so that the user can interact with the FPGA during the development phase. This interface is created by adding a module to the FPGA design and specifying the number of module input and output ports to use. Chipscope has a server feature to allow debugging from an internet connected computer separate from the computer that is connected to the FPGA. Xilinx also includes a command line interface to send commands to the FPGA. On a Microsoft Windows XP system batch commands can start and stop the Chipscope server and setup the Tcl (Tool Command Language) interface. Tcl is an open source scripting language that helps to quickly use commands in the Chipscope API (application programming interface). The Chipscope Tcl routines enable the user to connect to the FPGA through JTAG and lock that connection until the script finishes. The Tcl script finishes using commands to un-lock the JTAG connection to the FPGA.

Fig. 5: Block diagram of how the lab is made available to remote students through the web.

The web interface was designed to allow remote users to perform experiments using a computer connected to the internet with a web browser. Everything else must be transparent to the remote user. In order to achieve this goal the web interface design needs to satisfy three main requirements. First, only the standard HTTP (hyper text transfer protocol) port is used so that remote users do not have to change any of their own settings. They also will not

have to try to get an administrator to fix firewall issues. Second, the remote user does not need to install client software on his or her machine. The Adobe Flash plug-in is used to display the live video from an Adobe Flash Media Server. This is a standard plug-in already needed for a high proportion of web pages displaying any type of animation or video. Third, the instructor must be able to easily add remote laboratory experiments and update them quickly. This is accomplished using Java Server Page technology in a modular approach with simple modules created to do various things, such as upload a file, on/off push button, and

parameter field. These separate modules can be combined as needed in one web page.

The web development is accomplished using the Netbeans development environment. Java Server Pagelets can be created and combined with other pagelets. Java server pages and pagelets are rendered to HTML code by the server and sent to the remote user's browser. The remote user does not need to install the Java Virtual Machine environment or make sure that it is at the correct version.

Fig. 6: Remote web interface for the DC motor laboratory example: control window.

IV. EXAMPLE OF A SIMPLE DL LABORATORY: SPEED CONTROL OF A DC MOTOR

Over the past four years the SDC has been used in the NPS power laboratory to offer state of the art power electronics and drive hardware set ups to resident students for laboratory exercises and MS theses experiments. Power electronics experiments include: buck and boost converters, diode rectifiers, H-bridge inverters, series loaded resonant

DC-DC converters, three phase inverters and double bridge regenerative AC/AC converters. Motor drives include variable speed control of induction machines, doubly fed induction motor drives for wind power and ship propulsion applications. Each topology can be set up with different controllers and modulators due to the flexibility of the SDC.

Applying the method described in the previous section these laboratories can be offered to non-resident students taking the distance learning power electronics and electric

machines classes. These classes comprise a certificate offered at NPS; ‘Electric Ship Power Systems Area’ [19].

As a proof of concept a simple laboratory experiment exercising a separately excited DC motor drive was implemented as the first DL laboratory. The successful implementation of this remotely controlled laboratory is presented in the following subsections. First, the theory and simulations used in class are presented, then the remote control laboratory operation is shown to complete the student’s educational experience as part of the Electric Machines curriculum.

A. Analysis and Simulations

The goal of the DC motor drive laboratory is to reinforce the basic concepts learned during the lectures: separately excited DC motor operation open loop and with IR drop compensation to achieve constant speed operation with changing load.

The equations which represent a separately excited DC motor are found in the textbook [18]. Equation (1) represents the field circuit on the stator, (2) the armature circuit on the rotor and (3) the torque equation with the assumption that I_f is constant or the field is a permanent magnet.

$$V_f = R_f I_f \tag{1}$$

$$V_a = r_a I_a + \omega_r L_{AF} I_f = r_a I_a + \omega_r k_v \tag{2}$$

$$T_e = L_{AF} I_f I_a = k_v I_a \tag{3}$$

From the electric machines theory the students learn that as the load increases the DC motor speed decreases due to the resistive or “IR” losses represented by the term $r_a I_a$ in (2) because I_a is increasing as the torque increases.

In order to maintain constant speed independent of load changes a simple feedback control loop can be implemented for the buck converter controlling the armature voltage of the DC motor:

$$V'_a + r_{a_est} I_{a_meas} = V_a = r_a I_a + \omega_r L_{AF} I_f = r_a I_a + \omega_r k_v \tag{4}$$

Equation (4) shows that when the estimated resistance r_{a_est} is equal to the actual armature resistance, r_a , and also $I_{a_meas} = I_a$, then the motor speed does not change when the load (I_a) changes:

$$V'_a = \omega_r L_{AF} I_f = \omega_r k_v \tag{5}$$

Fig. 7 shows a block diagram implementing the feedback control, indicated as IR compensation, demonstrated by the above equations.

The analysis is reinforced by simulations performed using Matlab/Simulink physics based models of the DC motor and its control. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the simulated speed and torque curves of a separately excited DC motor without and with IR compensation respectively. The simulations show in a graphic format what the analysis has demonstrated through

equations (1)-(5); the DC motor speed drops when the load is doubled, at simulation time $t=12$ seconds, unless an IR compensation control is implemented.

Fig. 7: IGBT A+ gate drive generation with IR compensation

Fig. 8: Speed and torque with load doubled at $t=12$ s and no IR compensation

Fig. 9: Speed and torque with load doubled at $t=12$ s and with IR compensation

The next step for the students is the experimental validation. In particular an experimental laboratory demonstrates the speed variation of a motor without IR

compensation and the behavior of the same motor with IR compensation. The laboratory experiment also shows the students the difference between ideal simulations, where $r_{a_est}=r_a$ and real hardware where a r_{a_est} is merely a good, but not exact, estimate of the actual armature resistance, r_a .

B. Experimental Verification via Remote Lab Operation

Fig. 10 shows a block diagram of the lab set up including the voltage and current sensed and fed back to the control board. The DC bus voltage, V_{dc} , is sent to the FPGA and then displayed in the web interface, while the armature current feedback is used for the IR compensation control loop.

Fig. 10: block diagram of the DC motor drive laboratory set up

Three buck converters are used to control the motor; one for the field, one for the armature of the DC motor and the third one to control the dynamometer load. The field voltage is generated by the buck converter of leg B which utilizes the IGBT B+ and the diode B- in the power module shown in Fig. 10. The duty cycle for the IGBT B+ is set to a constant. The output of the buck converter on leg A is applied to the armature of the DC motor as shown in Fig. 10. When the IR Compensation option is off, the duty cycle is defined by the user by choosing one of the two available speed settings (ref. Fig. 6). When the IR Compensation feature is on, the gate drive signal for the IGBT A+ is generated as shown in the diagram of Fig. 7. By adding the $r_a I_a$ term to the commanded voltage, the speed of the DC motor is no longer affected by changes in the load. Leg C of the voltage source inverter is used as a buck converter to vary the load connected to the DC machine. For this experiment the buck converter duty cycle can be varied within the 0 to 35% range.

The remote student executes the laboratory exercise using the web interface shown in Fig. 6. On the top left corner there are four tabs corresponding to four pages that are available to support the lab experiment. The instructions for executing the laboratory and writing the laboratory report are

accessed by selecting the tab “Lab Overview” on the top left corner of the website. The “Help” window provides additional support with a recorded video describing in details the features of the laboratory website.

Fig. 6 shows the laboratory control interface page which includes the hardware control window and the live video window displaying in real time what is happening to the hardware. The control window on the left includes the commands to program the FPGA, turn on/off the DC motor, change the commanded speed, select different loads and turn on/off the IR voltage drop compensation. By pushing the “Get Motor Speed” button the real time speed of the DC motor is displayed. After collecting the speed data for the different types of loads under different speed and control conditions the students plot the data as shown in Fig. 11. The experimental data plotted in Fig. 11 reinforces the concepts learned by the students in class from the electric machine theory’s equations and computer simulations presented in the previous section; the motor speed drops significantly as the motor load increases without compensation. The addition of IR compensation makes the speed almost unaffected by load changes.

Fig. 11: Experimental data plot: DC motor speed vs. load.

Field and armature current measurements are performed using the oscilloscope, a Tektronix MSO-4034 Mixed Signal Oscilloscope, which is connected to the internet. Such web enabled oscilloscope is controllable remotely and reads data from current and voltage sensors which displays to the main web server by its embedded web server. The oscilloscope’s web page is accessed by selecting the “Oscilloscope” tab in Fig. 6 and is shown in Fig. 12. The screen capture was made when the settings are those shown in the control panel in Fig. 6; speed setting #1, 20% load duty cycle and no IR compensation. The waveform on top of Fig. 12 (channel 2) displays the differential voltage probe output V_a , therefore it shows the armature voltage duty cycle which is set by the speed selection in Fig. 6. The second waveform from the top

in Fig. 12 (channel 1) of the oscilloscope displays the differential voltage probe output V_c , therefore it shows the load duty cycle, controlled by the buck converter on leg C of Fig. 10. In this case the duty cycle is set to 20%. The third waveform from the top in Fig. 12 (channel 4) displays the field current. Finally the bottom waveform (channel 3) displays the DC motor armature current. By using the oscilloscope measuring tools the student can record the average field and armature current measurements and create plots similar to the speed plot shown in Fig. 11. The students can also verify the duty cycles of the buck converters on leg A and C.

Fig. 12: Oscilloscope webpage screen capture. Top to bottom: voltage V_a (ch2), voltage V_c (ch1), field current I_{field} (ch4), armature current $I_{armature}$ (ch3).

V. THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF THE SDC

The SDC based hardware set ups have been in use in the NPS laboratories for four years and received enthusiastic approval from the resident students, before a web interface was designed to accommodate the DL curriculum. Each laboratory includes simulation and hardware experience, as shown in the simple example presented in section IV. Typical laboratories are more complex than the DC motor drive example shown in this paper, including different types of power converter topologies, modulation strategies and control. The students simulate the power converter using a Simulink/Matlab model provided, then compare the simulated waveforms to the experimental waveforms acquired in the laboratory. Experimental data acquired through the oscilloscope web server is imported into Matlab for post-processing such as FFT analysis. The students enjoy the oscilloscope's web interface.

The success of the new laboratories can be measured by an increased score in the student opinion forms (SOFs) for the question 16 (Q16) "Overall, I would rate the laboratories". As an example for the EC3150 course entitled "Solid State Power Conversion" the average SOF score for question #16

(Q16) was 3.7/5.0 over the academic years 2002 through 2006 before the new laboratories were used. During the academic years 2007 through 2009, when the SDC based laboratories were assigned to the students the average score increased to 4.6/ 5.0.

The number of students taking the course has also registered a 40% increase over the sampled three years. Student's satisfaction has been high also with the MS theses experimental projects made possible by the SDC.

On the wave of this success with the resident students, remote laboratories such as the DC motor drive presented in this paper are being developed and will be offered in future DL courses.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A novel hardware laboratory set-up has been designed and presented in this paper. The hardware is activated by a computer communicating with an FPGA based control system. The student's positive feedback over the past four years has stimulated the development of a web interface for the laboratory set-up. The goal is to make power electronics and drives laboratories accessible to remote students taking distance learning courses. The laboratory web interface presented in this paper does not require the student to install any specific software on his/her computer; only a web browser is needed. Distance learning students can run the experiment and acquire oscilloscope waveforms with minimum assistance from a lab technician who turns on the power and supervises the lab equipment for safety.

A simple DC motor drive laboratory is presented in this paper as an example of a successfully implemented laboratory that can be executed by remotely located students via a web interface.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge Prof. Emeritus Jeff Knorr's encouragement in the development of the new SDC based power laboratories and their application to distance learning education. We also wish to thank the Naval Postgraduate School's Center for Educational Design, Development, and Distribution (CED3) for its support and especially Tom Mastre, the Director, and Diane Jones who wrote the html code for the DC motor laboratory webpage.

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